

ATTRACTING STUDENTS TO WORK ON THE TEXT IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL READING LESSONS IS A KIND OF PEDAGOGICAL JAROYON

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Annotation: The article describes the idea that the historical progress of a personality society is growing from the simplest to a complex, multifaceted social relationship. If the simplest ties are based on the fact that seed members in the primitive community system in many cases transmit information to each other about the source of food, the risks that arise, directions for organizing actions, complex, multifaceted social relations – in the process of production, service, education, health, security, fulfillment of civil obligations (for example, payment of taxes) are visible in the organization of The correct, rational organization of social relations ensures, firstly, that the issue being resolved has a positive solution, secondly, that time is saved, and thirdly, that the process of intimate communication occurs.

Keywords: speech cultivation, work on the text, oral and written speech, communication, word meaning, speech.

Attracting students to work on the text in the primary class is considered a pedagogical process that manifests its own characteristics. When working on the text in elementary grades, such as any pedagogical process, it is necessary to take into account certain psychological, pedagogical, methodological requirements. Only then will elementary students acquire the skills and abilities of mastering certain knowledge, reading fluently and consciously by working with the text, speech becomes richer, thinking skills develop. As a result, the requirements provided for in the curriculum are met.

The texts given in the "reading book" textbooks are a tool in the formation of speech skills in elementary school students. The main purpose of reading lessons in elementary grades is to prepare students to correctly understand the content of the text, to be able to read consciously and expressively, to perceive the information given in the text, to react to the reality expressed in the text. Accordingly, the elementary school teacher carries out methodological training according to the purpose of the lesson, the content of the material under study, the level of available knowledge, skills, qualifications of students. When preparing readers for reading the text of a work, the emphasis is primarily on introducing them to the subject, language, ideological content and artistic-

aesthetic value of the text, drawing an appropriate conclusion from the content of the text. Reading activity is also a special manifestation of speech.

How meaningful, accurate and correct a student can express his opinion allows you to determine the level of his educational-cognitive activity, skills and qualifications. Questions and tasks set in reading lessons on the perception and assimilation of the content of the text should make students think, focus on the use of phrases, artistic image tools used by the author when answering, encourage them to use new words and phrases for themselves more in speech.

Possession of the skill of reading the text, in turn, is considered one of the important factors that enrich the speech of the reader.

Any lesson that is an independent part of teaching serves to fulfill an educational, developmental and educational goal. The overall goal of any course is to “give students knowledge and achieve the level at which they can put the knowledge they receive into practice, to form the qualities inherent in the perfect personality in each student.

The didactic requirements for “reading” classes in the “state educational standards of general secondary education” on primary education begin with the focus of student attention on what to learn and what to remember.

By working on the text, teaching students to be creative, independent and logical in observation, to analyze the text and be able to express their attitude towards it requires great skill from the teacher.

In children aged 7-9 years, “written speech also begins to form... Based on the occupation of written speech, information about various texts occurs in them. Since written speech has just begun to form during this period, children will not yet have developed enough skills in controlling the thoughts, words and letters that they write. Alternatively, he is given the opportunity to create. Independent creative work generates in elementary school students the ability to understand the given topic, determine its content, collect information to state their opinion, distinguish important aspects, implement it in a certain sequence, draw up a plan. The correct composition of sentences, finding words that correspond to exactly this content and writing them correctly, correctly placing punctuation marks, being able to find and correct their own circumstances are calculated from the indicators of mental development”.

Before reading stories on a historical topic, the teacher determines the students' knowledge of the history of the motherland and the great siymos of its glorious past.

Preparatory work before reading poetic texts is much more complicated. The task of a holistic perception of lyrical works is to create a harmonious mood for the poet's psyche, to stimulate the reader's feeling of joy, admiration, sadness along with the poet. In this, the teacher's

the introduction is short, goal-oriented and to enter the world of the poet should be supportive.

In elementary school reading classes, the teacher's introduction is one of the leading links in pre-reading preparation of the text, and the effectiveness of spiritual and moral education largely depends on its correct organization.

2. Reading the text and analyzing it. In the process of reading the text, readers get acquainted with its ideological and artistic features, with the events reflected in the work. In this case, it is possible to train the text in expressive, interpretive and roles, depending on the genre characteristics of the work. Reading the artistic text helps to accurately visualize the landscapes described by the author, draw appropriate conclusions from the behavior of the heroes of the work.

"The main purpose of the analysis is to understand the essence of the artistic world embodied in the work, to correctly and fully perceive its original content." Analysis is an important factor in guiding students to creative and independent thinking. Readers, in the process of analysis, express their opinion on the events described in the work, learn the meaning of unfamiliar words, fully understand the content of the text.

In fact, " the chief issue of literary analysis is the analysis conducted by working on the text. When the reader gets acquainted with the content of the work during the reading, he refers to its poetics during the analysis. While Mutolaa enriches the emotion and regains the mind, the analysis helps to delve into the meaning in the text tagzamin " [1]

Although the main focus in the process of working on the text in reading lessons is on its content, the structure should not be overlooked either. In particular, the reader, who realized that past, present or next-time forms are used in the image of the conditions under which the event is taking place, the landscape, the pastimes, the psyche of the heroes of the work, is not mistaken in the oral narration of the content of the text. Focusing readers ' attention on the fact that in the image of phenomena of one content in the text (landscape, mental state, portrait of a literary hero), characterizations are usually in the form of one tense, helps to form not only their skills associated with reading and writing, but also with the perception and thinking of the content of the text.

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